

A MODERN APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH ACTIVITY IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: In the current process of rapid globalization, a number of practical works are being carried out by pedagogues and researchers in order to carry out the education system organically and efficiently. Including in the preschool education system, large-scale work is being carried out in order to make preschool children perfect in all aspects.

Key words: child, environment, research, activity, approach.

Research activity in preschool children can be carried out in several directions, depending on the age and individual characteristics of all groups of preschool children. For this, it is necessary to develop scientific research adapted to preschool children. As an example, the study "Milk and milk products". At the beginning of this study, it is necessary to introduce children to milk and milk products, to introduce the effective aspects of this product to the child's body. This study should be adapted to an older group of children. The purpose of this research is to know the importance of dairy products for the normal growth of the child's body, to develop the ability to work in a team and cognitive interest in children. The research is carried out in several stages.

In addition, it is possible to conduct scientific research on the topic of "Winter Season" in order to develop research and care for nature in children of preschool age. The purpose of this is to form children's ideas about the seasonal changes of wildlife and inanimate nature in winter. development of monologue, dialogue, polological, coherent speech, replenishing vocabulary. It is to use various visual materials to depict winter nature, to help children develop their creative abilities, their imagination, logical thinking, and the ability to notice changes in nature. This research work is closely related to the daily life of preschool children. Nature itself provides material for observation, research, experience and creativity. Winter games, entertainment, wonderful holidays and imaginations of the holiday through words and creative activities allow the child to vividly express the image. In this process, it is possible to conduct research with preschool children in several ways. For example, the joint development of scenarios for holiday events (based on the child's imagination and creative approach).

Based on the above topic, we can conduct training in all types of pre-school educational organizations currently operating in our country, that is, in five types of activity centers. In our first language and speech center, we can observe how children express their imagination and knowledge through their speech by providing extensive and interesting information to children about the winter season using audio recordings, cartoons, fiction, proverbs, proverbs, riddles, illustrations, and reproductions of pictures.

The second center is the "Science and Nature Center" and in accordance with this center, we plan to inform children about natural phenomena (weather, seasons) using a number of educational technologies and carry out practical experiments. In the art center, it is appropriate to draw pictures, appliqué and clay works related to the winter season in order to

develop the artistic and creative abilities of children. The expected result is the development of aesthetic perception, color perception in children, improvement of technical skills in drawing, modeling, and application. To teach children to convey the image of winter in different techniques and to use different materials in drawing. In clay work, it is to carry out the work correctly and efficiently using different methods and materials.

In addition, it is planned to encourage independent creativity and imagination by learning songs about winter through music lessons and performing holiday dances. Of course, the results will be as effective as we expected.

Expected results are explained below. Expanding and enriching children's knowledge about seasonal changes in nature during the winter season. Formation of children's interest in knowledge during practical exercises together with the teacher. Formation of children's monologic, dialogue and coherent speech, enriching it with epithets, new words and phrases. Formation of artistic abilities of children during creative activities together with adults. Development of children's ability to use new winter games and amusements, to use them in independent play activities.

Reciting poems about winter. Involvement of parents in the creative process of working with children is to increase their interest in cooperation with the kindergarten.

Currently, in connection with the revision of the priority forms and methods of teaching in preschool educational organizations, the methods that develop the abilities of children for the initial forms of generalization, conclusion and abstraction prevail. and this method is called experiment.

Another aspect is independent learning, its characteristics, recognition of something that the child did not think about or guessed before, is not yet in his power. The task of adults is to help children to form an active desire to experiment, to create optimal conditions for the development of creative, independent and joint activities of children through various experimental and artistic activities..

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